

D7.1		
Communication and Dissemination Plan		
Submission Date 2023.06.30	Version 2.0 – Approved by EC	
	PU	Public X
Due Date 2023.06.30	SEN	Sensitive
	R-UE/UE-R	EU classified
Deliverable Title	Communication and Dissemination Plan	
Deliverable No.	D7.1	
Lead beneficiary	MWS	
Contributing WP	WP7	
Type	R – Document, report	
	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01 Grant Agreement: 101094397	

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13628430

Project Full Title	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
Project Acronym	CRAFT-OA
Project No.	101094397
Start Date	2023.01.01
End Date	2025.12.31
Duration	36 Months
Project Website	https://craft-oa.eu
Authors	Sona Arasteh (https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5725-1922), Tabea Klaus (https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2791-1053), Kristina Posavec (https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0449-6325), Martina Dvorakova (https://orcid.org/0009-0004-6521-2773), Sy Holsinger (https://orcid.org/0009-0005-8978-225X)
Abstract	<p>This deliverable outlines the overall communication and dissemination plan (CDP) for the CRAFT-OA project. The CDP describes the project and its targets, the objectives for its communication and dissemination (C&D) activities and presents a stakeholder analysis. Furthermore, the CDP explains the project's C&D strategy and gives an outlook on C&D measures already initiated and planned for the future. The strategic approach, internal and external communication activities and a KPI table are presented in this document.</p> <p>Additionally, the deliverable outlines its intertwinement with D7.2 "Exploitation and Sustainability Plan", due for M18, identifies potential risks and threats to the C&D goals and gives an overview of the collaboration among CRAFT-OA, PALOMERA, and DIAMAS.</p>

Version and Revision History

Version	Date	Author/Reviewer/Contributors	Comments
0.1	2023.06.12	Authors: Sona Arasteh (MWS), Sy Holsinger (OPERAS AISBL), Tabea Klaus (UGOE), Kristina Posavec (SRCE)	Full initial draft
0.2	2023.06.16	Reviewer: Aleš Pogačnik (ZRC SAZU)	1st review
0.3	2023.06.27	Reviewer: Margo Bargheer (UGOE)	2nd review
0.4	2023.06.29	Authors: Sona Arasteh (MWS), Sy Holsinger (OPERAS AISBL)	Final review
0.5	2023.06.30	Contributors: Tabea Klaus (UGOE), Theresa Waldmann (UGOE)	Final formal check
1.0	2023.06.30		Submitted version
1.1	2024.07.19	Theresa Waldmann (UGOE), Lisa Müller (UGOE)	Correction of formal mistakes, e.g. spelling mistakes
2.0	2024.07.19		Approved by EC

Disclaimer

CRAFT-OA is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement no. 101094397. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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List of Acronyms

C&D	Communication and Dissemination
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
D	Deliverable
DDH	Diamond Discovery Hub
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FHH	Freie Hansestadt Hamburg
HE	Horizon Europe
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IPSPs	Institutional Publishing Service Providers
IPTPs	Institutional Publishing Technology Providers
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KOALA	Konsortiale Open-Access-Lösungen aufbauen Consortial Solutions for Financing Open Access
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche Association of European Research Libraries

M	Month
OA	Open Access
PALOMERA	Supporting the Development of Aligned Policies for Open Access Books and Monographs
PI	Principle Investigators
PKP	Public Knowledge Project, Canada
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
T	Task
TB	Technical Board
TIB	Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology University Library
UGOE	Georg-August-Universität Göttingen
WP	Work Package

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 7.1 “Communication & Dissemination Plan” (CDP) describes the methodological approach behind CRAFT-OA (Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access) communication and dissemination (C&D) activities, their objectives and outlines an action plan for C&D activities. The CDP is a living document and will be updated twice: in June 2024 and December 2025.

The primary objective of the CRAFT-OA project is to enhance the Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing ecosystem. This will be achieved through the implementation of technical enhancements for journal platforms and software, the establishment of communities of practice to drive overall infrastructure improvement, and the promotion of greater visibility and recognition for Diamond OA publishing. Accordingly, the objectives for the C&D activities in CRAFT-OA are, firstly, to inform and engage stakeholders and the Diamond OA community; secondly to support the exploitation and sustainability of results and, thirdly, to create overall awareness for Diamond OA publishing models.

Methodologically, the CDP parallels the management approach of CRAFT-OA and focuses on agile development methods: Continuous feedback loops, small task forces working on single tasks and close collaboration with fellow projects, stakeholders, and the Diamond OA community guarantee maximum flexibility, innovativeness and pragmatism.

The baseline for the action plan developed in chapter 3 is the stakeholder analysis conducted in chapter 2. In the analysis, relevant stakeholders of the project are identified and mapped in a Power/-Interest Grid to allow for more efficient communication measures. According to this, the most important stakeholders to manage closely have been identified to be: Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) & Institutional Publishing Technology Providers (IPTPs), Policymakers, European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), research infrastructures, diamond OA journals, developers, libraries and publishing initiatives/projects within academia. Additionally, an initial engagement plan for stakeholders was set up that lists communication measures, channels and, wherever feasible, tasks, work packages (WP) and partners connected to specific stakeholders.

The general strategic approach of all C&D activities is to stay in close contact with the Diamond OA community through all of the four communication phases: 1) launching activities, engaging stakeholders, 2) informing and updating on ongoing activities, 3) disseminating final output, 4) maintain project results beyond funding. CRAFT-OA has set the strategic goal of establishing connections across various levels of community engagement. To accomplish this, the project's activities will be conducted at three distinct levels: 1) Europe, 2) associated countries, and 3) the wider international community.

The action plan for C&D activities described in chapter 3 differentiates among ‘internal communication’, ‘external communication’ & ‘outreach events’. This differentiation is pragmatic and allows for efficient task distribution. ‘Internal communication’ covers all C&D structure aimed to guarantee a continuous flow of information among consortium members (e.g. chat system, mailing lists, internal newsletter), while ‘external communication’ covers the structure set up for C&D measures and activities that informs and engages stakeholders

and communities about ongoing developments, results and opportunities to take part in the project (e.g. project website, social media, fact sheets). ‘Outreach events’ serves as an umbrella term for all event participations and organisations by consortium members that act as an opportunity to promote CRAFT-OA and its results. Chapter 3 also includes a Key Performance Indicator (KPI) table including KPIs such as social media followers and posts, blog posts, communication campaigns etc.

Chapter 4 “Exploitation and Sustainability” gives an outlook and deliverable “Exploitation and Sustainability Plan” due in June 2024. The section explains CRAFT-OA’s Key Exploitable Results (KERs) will be identified by the results’ degree of innovation, their exploitability and impact and further outlines the initial strategy to identify workflows and tools for the documentation of results.

The following chapter 5 “Risks/Threats” identifies potential threats to the success of C&D activities and potential solutions. As of now, four distinct risks & threats have been identified: 1) Stability of social media platforms, i.e. Twitter 2) Balancing stakeholder engagement, 3) spam filters, 4) multi-level community composition, i.e. reaching communities and initiatives on a national and international level alike. Potential solutions are: 1) creation of a Mastodon account run simultaneously, 2) continuous updates and involvement of the stakeholder analysis, 3) using several communication channels to spread information simultaneously, 4) use of project partners’ international and national networks for translation and dissemination of information.

Lastly, chapter 6 outlines the alignment of C&D activities among the projects CRAFT-OA, Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication ([DIAMAS](#)) and Supporting the Development of Aligned Policies for Open Access Books and Monographs ([PALOMERA](#)) expressed in activities such as a joint webinar series called “Community-driven Pathways to Equitable, Open Scholarly Publishing”, a cross-project communication task force. Furthermore, CRAFT-OA and DIAMAS share an International Advisory Board composed of 14 external experts in Open Science coming from all parts of the world to ensure fair global representation. The connection between DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA is also tangible in their contribution to the Capacity Centre for Diamond OA publishing: DIAMAS will contribute to the development of the Capacity Centre for Diamond OA publishing, along with CRAFT-OA (WP 1, 2, and 7). Updates on the development will be included in the updates of the CDP.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Project Description

CRAFT-OA stands for Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access. The project's 23 partners are from 14 European countries. The project aims to consolidate the Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing landscape by providing technical improvements for journal platforms and journal software, building communities of practice to foster overall infrastructure improvement, increasing visibility and recognition for Diamond OA publishing and integrating Diamond OA publishing with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and other large-scale data aggregators. Diamond OA is understood as a publishing model that neither generates fees for authors nor readers with the institutional sector (e.g. universities, research institutions, and libraries) providing the technological infrastructure needed for publishing. Over the project's life span from January 2023 to December 2025, CRAFT-OA will deliver technical and community tools, training events, training materials, information and services for the Diamond OA institutional publishing environment.

2.2 Deliverable Description

This deliverable 7.1 “Communication and Dissemination Plan”, henceforth called “CDP”, outlines the overall CDP for the CRAFT-OA project. While serving as a guideline and framework for the communication and dissemination (C&D) activities of the project, D7.1 is a living document, supporting the project's C&D activities during the entire project. This deliverable will be updated twice during the project, the first, D7.5, in M18. The second update is due at the end of the project in M36. The CPD is closely related to D7.2 “Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results”, due in M18.

The CDP describes the project and its targets, the objectives for its C&D activities and presents a stakeholder analysis. Furthermore, the CDP explains the project's C&D strategy and gives an outlook on C&D measures already initiated and planned for the future. Chapter 3 of the deliverable is presenting the current action plan for C&D activities. Chapter 3 lays out the strategic approach, internal and external communication activities and presents a Key Performance Indicator (KPI) table based on this approach and the stakeholder analysis conducted in chapter 2.

In the last third of the CDP, the chapter “Exploitation and Sustainability” outlines the intertwinement of the CDP with D7.2 “Exploitation and Sustainability Plan”, due at M18, followed by a section identifying potential risks and threats to the C&D goals and, finally, an overview on how the close collaboration with the projects [PALOMERA](#) and [DIAMAS](#) connects to all C&D activities. The CDP supports the CRAFT-OA consortium in conducting C&D in a transparent and structured way, shows pathways of how interested stakeholders can get informed or involved and strengthens the project's accountability vis-a-vis the EC and the wider public.

2.3 Objectives

The CDP not only outlines the strategic approach for C&D activities, the document also designs a framework that serves as a guideline for all C&D activities planned for the future. The CDP supports all members of the direct CRAFT-OA consortium in conducting C&D in a transparent, structured way and shows pathways of how interested stakeholders can get informed or involved as community representatives. Thus, it strengthens the project's accountability vis-a-vis the EC and the wider public. To adapt to the needs of the project's target groups and outer circumstances such as paradigm shifts in OA publishing, this framework or, respectively, guideline is by no means unchangeable. The CDP will be available as updated versions twice throughout the project (M18 and M36) to adjust the plan to reach the C&D objectives accordingly. These objectives are to:

- Inform stakeholders about the project's progress, development and results
- Create awareness for Diamond OA
- Support the sustainability and exploitation of the project results
- Promote the project's results and ensure their visibility, accessibility and availability
- Engage the OA community, thereby contributing to the creation and consolidation of a "community of practice"
- Guarantee a continuous flow of information among the consortium members

2.4 Preparation & Methodology

A detailed stakeholder analysis constitutes the groundwork for the strategy outlined in this document. The analysis draws from the target groups identified in the grant agreement and builds on that basis. A task force was created to conduct the analysis and met to discuss an initial draft provided by the T7.4 leader before discussing the edited version within work packages (WP) 7. The analysis collected via the stakeholder analysis includes a ranking of the importance and power of the stakeholders identified and defines a clear target of the interaction with the respective stakeholder (see chapter 2). Additionally, the analysis identifies communication channels between the project and those stakeholders. The analysis also includes a description of action listing the actions to be carried out regarding each stakeholder. If possible, responsibilities are defined clearly by naming relevant tasks, partners and WPs.

The actions identified for each stakeholder serve as a toolkit for the CDP. The general structure of the CDP was discussed and agreed on in an initial meeting of the task force dedicated to writing the CDP and the "Communication Toolkit". C&D activities were agreed to be separated conceptually along the lines of internal and external communication. 'Outreach' was defined as a category of communication covering events open to the public, organised by the CRAFT-OA consortium, as well as the participation of consortium members in conferences, workshops, etc.

With the CRAFT-OA project working closely with related projects such as DIAMAS and PALOMERA, the task force also agreed to include a section outlining the potential, planned actions and organisation of C&D activities that arise from collaborations with other projects.

Methodically, the CDP and the actions described in this document follow the values and principles of agile development with a strong focus on adaptability, community involvement, and a commitment to teamwork. Therefore, the stakeholder analysis following in chapter 2 marks the foundation for an overall participatory communication approach that is based on continuous collaboration with the Diamond OA community and fellow projects.

3 STAKEHOLDER ANALYSIS

The foundation for the actions and measures described in the following sections is a stakeholder analysis conducted by WP7 in May 2023. The analysis results include:

- A list of stakeholders identified
- A Power/Interest grid
- A description of action
- Identification of WPs involved and tasks connected

3.1 Stakeholders

The following stakeholder groups have been identified:

- EOSC Association & related networks
- Citizen Scientists and Citizen Science Principle Investigators (PIs)
- Diamond OA Journals¹
- Software developers
- Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs)
- Institutional Publishing Technology Providers (IPTPs)
- Research libraries
- Publishing initiatives/projects in academia
- Researchers
- Research Infrastructures
- Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)/Funders
- Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) service providers in Diamond OA
- Policymakers

The stakeholder groups identified represent all actors potentially involved in the success of the project. Stakeholders such as the EOSC, research infrastructures, policymakers & RPOs/Funders are involved with the project on an infrastructural level. Researchers, Diamond OA journals, IPSPs, IPTPs and SME service providers in Diamond OA are involved in the development of the project and the design of the project's results. This close collaboration, especially with the different actors from the Diamond OA community is a central point of the project's layout: CRAFT-OA aims to create a feedback loop with stakeholders, to implement their needs and wants into the project results. Firstly, it ensures the project's developments align with current developments and activities within the community. Secondly, the close interaction with stakeholders from this community represents the concept CRAFT-OA explores as a project: to support and empower local institutional publishers by providing an array of technical innovations adjusted to their needs.

¹ This includes journal authors, editors, and reviewers.

3.2 Power/Interest Grid

To guide the interaction with the stakeholder groups identified, they have been organised in a so-called Power/Interest Grid. Each quadrant represents the efficient level of engagement for stakeholders located in it:

Figure 1: Power/Interest Grid CRAFT-OA

The C&D directed at certain stakeholder groups will consider this analysis, e.g. stakeholders located in the “Manage closely” and “Keep satisfied” quadrants will be targeted heavier than the ones in the “Keep informed” and “Monitor” quadrants.

3.3 Engaging Stakeholders

In the context of the stakeholder analysis, several opportunities have been identified to engage stakeholders in the project. On a general level, this includes participating in events that target the stakeholders of the project (see chapter 3.3), also by making use of consortium members' involvement in disciplinary, regional or national networks; creating information material such as guides and factsheets, organising summer schools (T2.3); participating in EOSC events, task forces and working groups; the final conference of the project and the creation of training materials and newsletters; the project website; social media activity.

The engagement of stakeholders in CRAFT-OA serves the specific purpose of supporting a community of practice. Therefore, C&D activities put focus on enhancing communication and collaboration among stakeholders from the Diamond OA landscape.

These specific approaches and actions have been planned for stakeholder groups:

- **EOSC**

As an INFRAEOSC project, CRAFT-OA is closely connected with the EOSC. WP6 "Journals' Data Reuse and Uptake in the EOSC" is dedicated to supporting the integration of Diamond OA publishers and IPSPs into the EOSC. While the EOSC is, per definition, a research infrastructure, the close connection of CRAFT-OA and the EOSC on a structural and conceptual level necessitates that the EOSC is treated as a stakeholder separate from the research infrastructures.

CRAFT-OA is also part of the Horizon Europe (HE) "Communication & Engagement" Working Group organised by the EOSC and contributes to the joint event calendar. Furthermore, as a member of this group, the CRAFT-OA communication team has access to the EOSC Forum, where it can post and share information throughout the EOSC community.

- **Citizen Scientists & Citizen Scientists PIs**

Via supporting and standardising the Diamond OA model, CRAFT-OA is a strong advocate for the accessibility of research and science in general. If closer involvement with this stakeholder is needed, they may be reached via engaging with the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA).

- **Diamond OA Journals**

Diamond OA Journals are the most important stakeholder group to achieve the project's aim. They are either addressed as stand-alone entities or as being part of an IPSPs service portfolio. They will be contacted via all communication channels available to the project. Furthermore, the data from the DIAMAS survey will be used to create an initial contact list of IPSPs to further engage them in the project's development.

For the stakeholder Diamond OA Journals, contributors like authors, reviewers and editors pose several opportunities to get in touch with the stakeholder (e.g. events, workshops, trainings). Furthermore, several members of the consortium are involved in Diamond OA Journals and can facilitate their professional networks for dissemination.

- **Software developers**

Software developers are crucial for the project for two reasons. Firstly, Diamond OA journals are almost entirely based on open source software with community governance. Thus, these developers need to be involved in the development and adaptation of results such as plugins, data models and interoperability frameworks. Secondly, the technological output of the project will only be sustainable and create a change for the better, if it is taken up and maintained beyond the funded period. Developers will be targeted a) by the participation of consortium members in events such as Public Knowledge Project, Canada (PKP) sprints (see chapter 3.3); b) by their inclusion in the development of the living handbook (T7.3). One of the two summer schools, conceptualised as a writing session for the living handbook, will be specifically targeted at developers.

- **IPSPs**

In addition to the measures described above, IPSPs will also be targeted via close collaboration with the DIAMAS project, using their dissemination channels as a waygate. In later stages of the projects, IPSPs will be targeted with a tailored communication campaign to subscribe to the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH) developed by WP5.

- **IPTPs**

C&D activities for IPTPs involve the summer school also targeting developers, and constant collaboration with the product-oriented WPs 3, 4, 5, and 6. Additionally, T7.2 “Technology Providers Community Setup” aims to establish a sustainable network of IPTPs that mirrors the IPSPs network created by the DIAMAS project. Taking stock from the CRAFT-OA Technical Board, established and coordinated by WP2, the network will expand beyond the project and thereby add to the C&D activities as well as be supported via a communication campaign dedicated to IPTPs.

- **Research Libraries**

With several university libraries being represented in the consortium (e.g. UGOE, Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology University Library (TIB), Freie Hansestadt Hamburg (FHH)), their participation in the project will be exploited for C&D purposes, participation in events such as the Bibliocon or the annual LIBER² conference that will also support the project’s outreach.

- **Publishing initiatives/projects in academia**

This stakeholder group overlaps with the IPSP stakeholder group. Projects and initiatives that are not directly publishing themselves (e.g. consortia such as KOALA) will mainly be targeted via general C&D activities. As the collaboration with the Diamond OA community will intensify over the course of the project, the CDP update in M18 will re-evaluate if a tailored campaign for “non-publishing” initiatives is necessary.

² Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries

- **Researchers**

As researchers are present in all stakeholder groups, as authors, editors, developers or policy makers, no tailored action is planned.

- **Research Infrastructures**

Relevant research infrastructures around scholarly data and publishing such as OpenAIRE and OPERAS are already part of the consortium and will use their networks to disseminate information among their communities. Beyond their networks, the communication channels of the EOSC (events, working groups, task forces, the Forum) will be used to disseminate information about the project.

- **RPOs/RFOs**

RPOs and RFOs will be targeted via publications such as policy briefs and guidelines in particular.

- **SMEs service providers in Diamond OA**

SMEs service providers will be targeted via the aforementioned measures dedicated to developers, IPSPS and IPTPs.

- **Policymakers**

As RPOs and RFOs, policymakers are targeted via policy briefs, guidelines and official project documentation, along with participation at specific events such as a funder forum.

4 ACTION PLAN

4.1 Strategic Approach

Strategically, the approach of CRAFT-OA's CDP focuses on community-driven C&D activities. Planned activities such as the living handbook, summer schools and the preparation of the toolkit are not simply being made *for* the OA institutional publishing community but *with* the community. Partly, the community is already included in all endeavours of CRAFT-OA because a large fraction of the consortium itself is involved in Diamond OA institutional publishing. CRAFT-OA's C&D efforts exploit that inherent connection to the very community the project aims to provide with technology and guidelines. Already existing networks will be used to disseminate information as well as to engage the community further in the project. All C&D activities are taking into account aspects of equity, diversity, gender equality and inclusivity, as well as aspects such as FAIRification, bibliodiversity and multilingualism.

With a strong commitment to community-building comes a focus on local (national) institutional publishing initiatives. Therefore, the key message to be transmitted in all communication endeavours is that CRAFT-OA is a community-driven project, that simultaneously a) involves the community in improving the OA publishing landscape and b) strengthens the community by connecting stakeholders and providing tools and guidelines. The milestone "Communication Toolkit" due in M7 (July 2023) will provide a more detailed overview of key messages and the project identity.

CRAFT-OA aims to connect different levels of community, which is why the C&D activities will be taking place on three levels: 1) Europe, 2) associated countries and 3) the wider international community; thereby serving as the link among initiatives based along the scale of these three levels, all C&D activities aim to contribute to global connection to foster the Diamond OA model.

To better organise and coordinate activities, C&D will be subdivided into four subsequent, yet overlapping stages:

Figure 2: Communication Phases

In the current, first phase, of the project’s communication phases activities are initiated and stakeholders are actively engaged with the stakeholder analysis being a crucial part of this phase. In the second phase, all stakeholders will be provided with information tailored to their interests. The third phase is dedicated to promoting the final outputs of the project, while the fourth and final phase of communication tends to the need of ensuring the project’s results will be maintained after the end of the project.

4.2 Communication & Dissemination Activities

This section will explain in further detail the mode of communication, what kind of information will be shared, and via which channels. The aforementioned “mode” of communication refers to how CRAFT-OA manages C&D. The C&D actions described in the following subchapters will introduce the categorisation into internal and external communication to serve as a pragmatic differentiation of communication modes.

CRAFT-OA has set up an integrated communication infrastructure that consists of the project website, a file repository, mailing lists, a platform for internal communication and social media accounts for external communication. The project communication infrastructure is a mechanism essential for the success of the project. It supports effective and efficient collaboration throughout the consortium and enables C&D activities beyond the project consortium.

4.2.1 Internal

Internal communication covers all communication conducted among consortium members. Two communication channels have been established to make day-to-day communication easier: Set up by WP1, mailing lists for each WP, the Technical Board and the Project Management Board serve as channels for general communication among consortium members. Moreover, a chat/messaging system, serves as a more informal communication channel for the consortium. To ensure that the consortium as a whole is updated on current developments of the projects, from June 2023 on, the WP7 team will distribute a bi-monthly newsletter that will be compiled by the WP leaders. To share research findings and build a collective bibliography, WP1 created a Zotero community for the project.

These C&D activities will be explained in more detail below.

Mailing lists

Several mailing lists have been set up to organise the project's internal communication. The lists are characterised by the nature of communication, as well as the methodology and organisation of the project:

- craft-oa.all@sub.uni-goettingen.de: communication to the whole consortium
- craft-oa.admin@sub.uni-goettingen.de: communication among the administration team
- craft-oa.listtb-owner@sub.uni-goettingen.de: communication among and coordination of the Technical Board
- craft-oa.coordination@sub.uni-goettingen.de: communication with coordination team
- craft-oa.communication@sub.uni-goettingen.de: coordinate C&D activities among coordination team and communication officer
- craft-oa.PMB@sub.uni-goettingen.de: Project Management Board (PMB) communication and coordination
- craft-oa.WP2@sub.uni-goettingen.de: communication among WP2 project partners
- craft-oa.WP3@sub.uni-goettingen.de: communication among WP3 project partners
- craft-oa.WP4@sub.uni-goettingen.de: communication among WP4 project partners
- craft-oa.WP5@sub.uni-goettingen.de: communication among WP5 project partners
- craft-oa.WP6@sub.uni-goettingen.de: communication among WP6 project partners
- craft-oa.WP7@sub.uni-goettingen.de: communication among WP7 project partners.

All partners are aware of their responsibility to keep their respective lists updated, as well as for informing the rest of the consortium about any changes.

Newsletter

An internal newsletter will be established and distributed to consortium partners to share news and updates on project activities and milestones with all partners on the CRAFT-OA project. It will be distributed via email and sent out every two months.

Internal newsletters will include a variety of content, such as:

- Project news and updates
- Important announcements (e.g. upcoming events, media presence, publications)
- Highlighting achievements or milestones in the project
- Training and development
- Engaging content (e.g. photos from events, project information)

The purpose of an internal newsletter is to keep partners informed and engaged, build a sense of community and belonging and encourage open communication within the CRAFT-OA project.

Mattermost

For quicker and more informal internal communication among project partners, CRAFT-OA is using the open-source messaging and collaboration platform Mattermost, hosted by project partner and WP7 lead, OPERAS. It allows team members to communicate via topic-related channels, direct messages and group messages. The service also supports file sharing. A project space has been created for CRAFT-OA, and all consortium members were called to join. An additional benefit of the service lies in the fact that CRAFT-OA's sister projects DIAMAS and PALOMERA are also using the same Mattermost instance as well. This alignment in internal communication allows for swift and seamless one-on-one, cross-project communication.

Zotero

The aforementioned Zotero community that was established for CRAFT-OA by WP1 ensures seamless availability and communication concerning research-related issues and resources by enabling the creation of a collective bibliography. By that, the Zotero community supports collaboration among consortium members as well as serves as a documentation of the scientific publications referenced and consulted.

4.2.2 External

The term “external communication” refers to all communication directed beyond the consortium. External communication refers to the exchange of information, ideas and messages outside of the CRAFT-OA project with the wider community which can include customers, clients, partners, shareholders and the general public. The goal of external communication is to establish and maintain positive relationships with stakeholders and to promote the project activities, vision and mission.

With successful external communication, the project will build trust and enhance visibility among the public and stakeholders. The project C&D materials called the project communication kit include the project website, fact sheet, project logo, favicon, presentation and poster template and Zoom background template.

Corporate Identity

CRAFT-OA's corporate identity is based on values such as openness, pragmatism, and community-orientation. Accordingly, the project logo uses a plain, simplistic visual design to symbolise the pragmatic essence of CRAFT-OA and its results. Furthermore, the project logo represents the project's strong connection to the EOSC by co-branding. The purple used in the EOSC logo is a nod to the involvement of OPERAS. The font used, Roboto Regular, features open curves while simultaneously featuring largely geometric forms and thereby serving as a token of the values of openness and pragmatism.

Figure 3: CRAFT-OA Logo

A detailed description of the project's corporate and visual identity for all C&D means will be part of the milestone "Communication Toolkit" due in June 2023.

CRAFT-OA official website

As of May 2023, the official website of the project is accessible at <https://craft-oa.eu>. The website is an essential communication tool for project dissemination activities. It provides up-to-date information about the project, its activities, liaisons and outcomes as well as access to CRAFT-OA social media accounts and a subscription option to the project newsletter. The website structure will be gradually expanded and reorganised with new categories and content to reflect the progress of the project, provide insights and effectively promote outcomes. All partners will be included and encouraged to provide content for the website about project activities that took place on the national level.

The initial design of the website assembles a starting page, a section for news and events, results of the project (e.g. deliverables, scientific publications) and general information about the goals, structure and outline of the project. Furthermore, the website will feature the project's press kit, which includes the communication toolkit as well as the project logos available for download. The availability of the press kit serves to ensure consistent project branding, thereby contributing to the awareness level of the project's outputs.

Figure 4: CRAFT-OA Homepage (craft-oa.eu)

Furthermore, the website features a mailing list that visitors of the website can subscribe to. This mailing list serves two purposes. Firstly, subscribers will receive updates on project developments and results, such as activities, goals, milestones, events and publications. Secondly, the public mailing list is a means to engage the community by disseminating calls for action and sharing opportunities to take part in the project. The external newsletter will not be sent out regularly but will be used to disseminate current information according to results, events or calls for participation as necessary.

The Matomo Analytics plug-in was installed to track KPIs such as visits, unique visitors and actions per visit, amongst others.

Social Media

In terms of social media presence, the WP7 team decided to create two social media channels for the project, Twitter and Mastodon. The creation of a Twitter channel for CRAFT-OA was initially discussed at the first face-to-face consortium meeting in March 2023. An informal survey conducted within the consortium via Mattermost confirmed the decision to create a Twitter channel. To the question “What social media do you use most often for professional communication?” that was posed as a poll in the general chat a majority of 12 out of 17 participants answered with “Twitter”. Other possible answers were: LinkedIn (4 votes), Mastodon (1 vote), Instagram (no votes), and TikTok (no votes). It was decided to open a Twitter account and a Mastodon account despite the higher number of votes for LinkedIn to complement the outreach of the Twitter account in the context of the migration of users from

Twitter to Mastodon.³ Additionally, Mastodon was selected because of its alignment with the project's overall values: The platform values privacy and it is a community-driven social media, also known for its commitment to open-source software. A more nuanced survey collecting information about social media usage is planned for M17; firstly, to check whether the social media activities conducted and channels used by the project are still functional and effective. Secondly, the survey aims to gather a detailed picture of the effectiveness of all communication channels the project uses. The design of the survey will be defined further from M9 on. It will take the then-defined Key Exploitable Results (KERs) into account as well as the C&D performance up to this point.

The Twitter channel @craftoa_project and the Mastodon account @craftoa@mastodon.online were set up, activated and announced publicly with the launch of the website in May 2023. Both social media accounts aim to support further project communication, maximise the project outreach and foster engagement with the project. More information on the methodology of tweeting/posting on behalf of CRAFT-OA will be included in the milestone “Communication Toolkit” due in M7.

Both accounts will be used frequently to post about project developments, engage with the community and announce project events.

Figure 5: CRAFT-OA Mastodon profile

Figure 6: CRAFT-OA Twitter profile

³ For the complementarity in terms of the target audience between Twitter and Mastodon see Chambers, T. (2022, December 2nd): A Snapshot of the #TwitterMigration, NEA Disinformation & Monitoring Report. Dewey Digital. <http://www.deweysquare.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/DSG-Snapshot-of-the-Twitter-Migration-December-12-2022.pdf>

Scientific Publications & Blog Posts

As the project progresses, more and more results will be achieved and published. Another means of external dissemination publishing the project's results in scientific journals or volumes. As of June 2023, one scientific publication has already been published:

- Bardi, A., Bargheer, M., & Manghi, P.: A Discovery Hub for Diamond Open Access publishing. *Information and Research Science Connecting to Digital and Library Science 2023. Proceedings of the 19th Conference on Information and Research Science Connecting to Digital and Library Science*. <https://eur-ws.org/Vol-3365/short12.pdf>

In total, the consortium aims to publish at least 12 scientific publications over the course of the project.

In addition, at least 5 blog posts will be written by the members of the consortium until the end of the project. The blog posts are supposed to highlight memorable events, developments and results of the project. Furthermore, they will focus on current discussions in the (Diamond) OA landscape and thereby help to engage the community.

Zenodo

A Zenodo community has been created for CRAFT-OA. The Communication Officers of the DIAMAS and the PALOMERA project have agreed that all publications will be published in all of the projects' communities to ensure maximum visibility throughout the target audience addressed by all of these projects.

Fact Sheet

For dissemination purposes, a fact sheet will be created that sums up key information (e.g. a brief summary of the project, project timeline, project partners) about the project, its methodology and the benefits for its target communities. The CRAFT-OA Fact Sheet is to be translated into several languages by the project partners to reach the local, and national communities. A printed version of the fact sheet will be sent to all partners to enhance dissemination through national channels.

External Communication via Stakeholders

All stakeholders are encouraged to share information and communication material shared with them, thereby working as communication amplifiers. One concrete example of external stakeholder involvement is the participation of consortium members in the EOSC Horizon Europe working group "Communication & Engagement" and the task force "Technology". Representing CRAFT-OA in these groups enables consortium members to spread information about the project's results and events as well as to foster collaboration with other HE projects.

4.3 Outreach Events

The term “outreach” includes all events organised by consortium members as well as external events consortium members take part in such as conferences, workshops or barcamps. As CRAFT-OA is a community-driven project, this segment of the CDP is closely connected to T2.2 “Community Support Framework” and T2.3 “Community Engagement”. WP2 will organise two summer schools (one of them already scheduled for the summer of 2024) and host a Public Knowledge Project Sprint (one of them already held in June 2023). WP7 will support WP2 via specific communication campaigns dedicated to these events.

All events consortium members take part in or organise are documented in a shared spreadsheet to prepare and align dissemination efforts for these events. To ensure a sufficient feedback loop, a form has been created to gather data on external events, capturing information such as audience size and target audience of the event.

As of June 2023, members of the consortium have already taken part in seven external events:

2023	Event	Event Type	Location	Contribution
20-21 June 2023	PKP Sprint	Other	Copenhagen	Other
19-23 June 2023	EGI2023	Conference	Poznań	Networking
15 June 2023	OPERAS Ger Open Chat	Open Chat	online	Q & A Session
15 June 2023	AUP Annual Meeting	Conference	online	Panel Discussion
23-26 May 2023	BiblioCon	Conference	Hannover	Presentation
16-17 May 2023	AEUP Conference	Conference	Tallin & Tartu	Other
28-30 March 2023	SRCE DEI 2023 conference	Conference	Zagreb	Poster

Table 1: Table representing CRAFT-OA event participation, June 2023

Furthermore, submissions have been made for the Open Science Fair in Madrid, the PUBMET2023 in Zadar, and the OAI13, all scheduled for September 2023. All of these submissions have been accepted. This year, consortium members will also participate in the annual LIBER conference (5-7 July), and the Global Summit on Diamond Open Access (23-27 October) in Mexico.

The CRAFT-OA final conference, scheduled for December 2025, will serve as the concluding outreach event of the project. The conference will be used to spotlight the results of the project, showcase the strong bond to the community the project nurtures and conclude the

transfer of the project's results into the hands of the community. The event will be communicated via all channels and networks available. More detailed information on the planning of the event and the C&D activity connected to it will follow with the updates for the CDP.

4.4 KPI Table

The table of KPIs will be updated and complemented in M18 when the first update of the CDP is due and the KERs of the project have been identified.

Action	Related KPIs	Target		
Communication of Project Results	#events	25 events with partners attending		
	#participants	50 participants per event		
	#organisations reached	100 participants at final conference		
	# training sessions at external events	10 digital training sessions		
Outreach & communication of project's concept & opportunities to engage with main target groups	# interactions in campaigns (e.g. on OPERAS, EOSC Future channel)	10 comments per campaign		
	# shares/retweets of promoted results (via other channels) Engagement with other users	25 retweets per campaign		
Communication of project outcomes and results	# clicks and downloads via a Zenodo community	1000 downloads at Zenodo		
	# blog posts through other channels	5 blog posts		
	#scientific publications	12 scientific publications		
Social Media		M18	M24	M36
	# Twitter Follower	350	500	600
	# Twitter Posts	100	200	450
	# Mastodon Follower	50	70	120
	# Mastodon Posts	30	60	100

Table 2: KPI table

5 EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

This section provides an early introduction to how CRAFT-OA will manage activities related to sustainability and exploitation. A full report will be provided in D7.2 “Exploitation and sustainability plan” at M18. For alignment purposes, exploitation means the use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including inter alia, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

5.1 Exploitation

For both consortium members as well as external stakeholders, it is important to distinguish between project results and KERs.

5.1.1 Project Results

Project results are generated during the project implementation. This may include: know-how, innovative solutions, algorithms, proof of feasibility, new business models, policy recommendations, guidelines, prototypes, demonstrators, databases and datasets, trained researchers, new infrastructures, networks, etc. They also include research roadmaps, policy recommendations, reports, platforms (collaboration), skills and knowledge, educational materials, codes of conduct, pre-standards, prototypes, software, publications and data.

There will be many project results, however, not all will require a full sustainability and exploitation strategy and plan or where project results are grouped as a Key Exploitable Result.

5.1.2 Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

The primary project results from the dissemination and exploitation point of view are the KERs. A specific note from the EC Portal states that before uploading a result in the Horizon Results Platform, to make sure that it is in fact a Key Exploitable Result, which defines a KER as: "Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights".

Therefore, CRAFT-OA will prioritise the identification of the main interesting results (as defined above), which will be selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be "exploited" – meaning to make use and derive benefits - downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or

education.

The following initial criteria will be used to select and prioritise these results:

- Degree of innovation
- Exploitability
- Impact

For CRAFT-OA, KERs will be identified during the life of the project with the aim of identifying them as early as possible. One starting point will be through the CRAFT-OA Technical Board (TB) where a product and service portfolio is being collated. This will be the first concrete contribution towards identifying potential KERs. The TB is composed of the 4 technical WPs where the main development activities are taking place in the project (WP3-WP6) and is coordinated by WP2.

KER Champion

For further refining and consolidating the collection of information required to fully analyse, articulate and disseminate, each of the KERs will be assigned a "KER champion". The role of the KER champion is to act as the central contact point for all issues that might arise related to a KER. The champion will help to coordinate and encourage the exploitation and dissemination of the KER. The champion will also act as the primary spokesperson for the KER and accept or suggest changes and improvements of the KER-related documentation, promotional material, and plans in collaboration with the different WP7 team members.

Documentation

The CRAFT-OA project management is currently evaluating various documentation management systems for the overall project knowledge base. Several requirements include functionalities that support not only static collection of information, but also the potential management of several project activities such as deliverables and milestones, action assignment as well as the use of templates that can be used to harmonise content. The consortium agreed that the project's documentation management system needs to meet European GDPR requirements, be intuitive and functional and support easy transition of internal communication to external documentation (e.g. software development, community building). One of the leading contenders is Confluence.

WP7, led by OPERAS, is currently using Confluence as its own internal Integrated Management System as well as offering it for other EC funding projects (i.e. OPERAS-PLUS, PALOMERA). If selected, or something similar, this would be how all sustainability and exploitation documentation would be collected and managed.

For structuring content, the Horizon Results Platform required set of information (i.e. Result Title, Target Audiences and Needs; About us; Result Description and Influence; Result and Business Maturity and exploitation outlook; and Investors Corner) will be used.

This approach offers the ability for information to be collaboratively worked on, always

transparent in its availability, while ensuring that the right information can be easily imported into the portal by the project's end.

Horizon Results Booster Service

Several consortium partners have had experience from previous projects (i.e. TRIPLE, COESO) running through the Horizon Results Booster⁴ service that offers expert, free-of-charge, support services to boost the exploitation potential of research results, disseminate effectively, and go to market. There are 3 different modules offered: Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy, Business Plan Development, and Go To Market.

It is expected that the initial use of the available templates will help guide the KER Champions to better articulate their exploitation plans. A formal request of the service will be evaluated as the project develops.

5.1.3 IPR Management

Intellectual property management is the management of an organisation's intellectual property (IP), including patents, trademarks, copyrights, and trade secrets. The goal of IP management is to maximise the value of an organisation's IP while minimising the associated risks, costs, and administrative burdens. IP management activities include protecting IP, licensing and monetizing IP, and leveraging IP to create new products and services.

The CRAFT-OA Consortium Agreement remains the reference document for the handling of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), whether as background or as foreground. However, any result of research, work, publication or invention that derives from the activities carried out within the scope of the CRAFT-OA project and is susceptible to economic exploitation or may give rise to a request for ownership of IPRs, the project management (WP1) shall be notified including the beneficiary representative. IPR will be evaluated on a case-by-case basis as necessary.

In addition, IPR will be explicitly analysed as part of the KER business and sustainability model.

5.2 Sustainability

To ensure organisational, technical and financial sustainability, each Key Exploitable Result will be individually assessed. However, as it is the CRAFT-OA mission to improve the technical and organisational infrastructure of Diamond OA, it will be essential to identify legal and administrative options that can provide the long-term sustainability of each KER. The OPERAS AISBL and wider RI could be a natural channel to be initially explored, however, all sustainability strategies need to be coordinated across the variety of projects and activities ongoing to fully realise the Diamond OA model (i.e. DIAMAS, PALOMERA) as well as the EOSC.

⁴ <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

Something that has already been taken advantage of with the GoTriple service as one of the main KERs from the TRIPLE project, where OPERAS serves as the legal host while also supporting the agreement structure. Though it does not necessarily have to be the mechanism that is used, it represents the possibility for KER to be continuously exploited where needed.

As mentioned in the introduction of this section, the content provided was to offer some initial strategies and approaches to addressing exploitation and sustainability, a full report will be provided in D7.2 “Exploitation and sustainability plan” at M18.

6 RISKS/THREATS

The C&D measures described above come with potential risks and threats, that have been identified as:

- **Twitter instability:** While Twitter remains the most powerful social media communication tool for academia, algorithm changes, modifications of the service's business model and whether the company complies with the obligations of the Digital Service Act may render it less (or un-)suitable to reach the target audience of the project. As a countermeasure, a Mastodon account has been created as the audience leaving Twitter is most likely to choose Mastodon as an alternative. Additionally, a more nuanced survey will be conducted in preparation for the first CDP update to fact-check the reach of the project's social media account.
- **Stakeholder Balancing:** A focus put on one stakeholder group may disadvantage communication efforts targeted at other stakeholder groups. The stakeholder analysis depicted in chapter 2 of this deliverable serves as a guideline on which stakeholders to target with which C&D activities at which point of the project. To ensure that the stakeholder analysis properly serves this function, the analysis will be checked for necessary updates in M18 and M24.
- **Spam filters (mailing list):** While the newsletter serves as a central communication measure to reach the OA community beyond the consortium, continuous information flow cannot be guaranteed only by the newsletter. Therefore, all information will be spread by several channels.
- **Community composition:** By design, consortium-transversal communication channels such as a Twitter account or a general newsletter do not directly target local communities of institutional publishing. To close this gap between general project communication and local communities, all partners of CRAFT-OA are involved in translating the general information disseminated via all project channels to their national, regional, disciplinary and local communities.

This initial list of risks and threats will be further explored in the update in M18. The first update of the CDP will also include a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, & Threats) analysis based on the identification of the project KERs and the update of the stakeholder analysis.

7 CROSS-PROJECT COLLABORATION

Conceptually, CRAFT-OA is closely connected to the HE projects [DIAMAS](#) and [PALOMERA](#) advocating for a community-driven and scholar-led publishing landscape. In the awareness that a sustainable OA infrastructure improvement and the strengthening of the European Research Area cannot be realised in isolation, the collaboration of the three projects was intended by the European Commission right from the start⁵. Another link between the three projects is their respective contribution to the EOSC, whether through direct or indirect services or through raising awareness and activating the scholarly publishing community for EOSC services.

Besides their thematic and conceptual proximity, the three projects are all either led by OPERAS itself or an OPERAS member coordinates the project and OPERAS is a member of the consortium, which facilitates cooperation across the domains of the projects (i.e. books and journals). The OPERAS network does not only provide an important community able to give feedback on project results and developments. In addition, each of the projects will share the results with the OPERAS community, which already ensures basic dissemination.

The close connection to both projects will be exploited to the advantage of all projects. For this reason, a cross-project communication task force has been created. Its core group consists of the communication officers of all projects, the extended group also includes coordination representatives from each project.

The planned webinar series “Creating Community-Driven Pathways to Equitable Open Scholarly Publishing with CRAFT-OA, DIAMAS, and PALOMERA” contains at least three 90-minute webinars conducted jointly among all projects that started on 20 June 2023.⁶ DIAMAS organised the first of these webinars. The responsibility for the organisation of these webinars will be rotated among the participating projects. The initial webinar aimed to engage the community and set the stage for the following webinars by giving the projects the possibility to present themselves: A presentation session at the beginning of the webinar allowed the coordinators of the project to highlight the aims, goals, alignments and complementarities among the projects. These presentations emphasized the focal point all projects have in common: to promote community-driven pathways to open scholarly publishing. The presentations were followed by a 45-minute panel session and a subsequent Q&A session. 191 people participated in the webinar. Later webinars will build on this initial presentation and cover more specific topics.⁷

Furthermore, a joint poster is in development that will feature all three projects visually aligned. The poster features key phases of the projects, participating institutions and the overarching topic of creating community-driven pathways to equitable open-scholarly publishing. It will be used for presentations covering all three projects.

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/faq/18726> and <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-infra-2022-eosc-01-02>

⁶ <https://www.craft-oa.eu/2023/05/craft-oa-diamas-palomera/>

⁷ A recording of the first webinar is available via the DIAMAS YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MujsbammMOW&t=3s>

Because of the similar focus and the conceptual complementarity of DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA both projects share their [International Advisory Board](#) composed of 14 external experts in Open Science coming from all parts of the world to ensure fair global representation. The members of the Advisory Board provide feedback on the projects' outputs, help guide the preparation of the Capacity Centre in a global context and support the alignment of the two projects.

Amongst others, DIAMAS will develop building blocks for the mentioned Capacity Centre that will provide information and support for Diamond OA publishing. CRAFT-OA, especially WP 1, 2 and 7, will contribute to the development of the Capacity Centre. An update of the results and the state of the development will be provided in the update of the Communication & Dissemination Plan.

8 LIST OF REFERENCES

Bardi, A., Bargheer, M., & Manghi, P. (2023). A Discovery Hub for Diamond Open Access publishing. *Information and Research Science Connecting to Digital and Library Science 2023. Proceedings of the 19th Conference on Information and Research Science Connecting to Digital and Library Science*. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3365/short12.pdf>

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